

ADAPTIVE MODELLING OF DELAMINATION GROWTH USING ISOGEOMETRIC CONTINUUM SHELL ELEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

As a means to decrease the complexity and size of numerical models for the simulation of progressive failure in composite laminates, and thereby also the computational time required for the simulations, we here propose an adaptive continuum shell element model based on the concept of Isogeometric Analysis. The concept based is based on the approach presented by Hosseini et al. [1], but in contrast to their work, in which delamination interfaces are predefined, we here address the need to handle successive introduction of new discontinuities in an automated fashion.

The formulation adopts T-spline basis functions for the discretisation of the shell mid-surface, whereas a higher-order B-spline functions are used for the interpolation in the thickness direction. A discontinuity can be incorporated in this latter function by so-called knot-insertion to account for ply interfaces (weak discontinuities) and delaminations (strong discontinuities). In order to automatically enhance the element, various stress-based criteria using element local improved interlaminar stresses can be used. However, for such a stress based approach, the prediction of the through-thickness variation of out-of-plane stress components needs to be improved if a coarse shell approximation is used (the so-called lumped state explained below). For this purpose, we propose and demonstrate the capability of a reconstruction technique based on the classical strategy of integrating the momentum balance equations. Due to the nature of the isogeometric analysis approximation and its higher order displacement smoothness over element edges, this reconstruction can be performed element-wise. This possibility to do an element-wise reconstruction is a strength compared to traditional shell elements, based on Lagrange approximations for the displacement field, for which displacement approximation derivatives (and thereby stresses) are non-smooth. In this way, the isogeometric continuum element can be used in an even more efficient fashion, allowing for the detailed analysis of large, thin-walled composite structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

A key to successful modelling of the complex progressive failure in layered composite materials is to have computationally efficient models and methods which can be adapted to the predominant failure mechanisms in each specific loading case. In particular, efficient approximation and solution methods for delamination modelling is crucial, since "high-fidelity" FE models with many elements through the component thickness interconnected with cohesive interface elements leads to unfeasible simulation times and memory requirements.

For that purpose, several papers have been published that present alternative methods for modelling concepts which support laminate failure analyses requiring only one shell element through the thickness and where arbitrary delamination propagation is accounted for only in areas where it is needed, cf. Hosseini et al. [1], Brouzoulis and Fagerström [2] and McElroy [3].

The proposed new concepts however need to be further developed before they can be readily applied to solve engineering problems in which delamination cracks can initiate and propagate. For traditional finite element based shell models, such as the one presented by Brouzoulis and Fagerström (based on

the eXtended Finite Element Method, XFEM), improved methods to predict the interlaminar stresses are needed for an accurate prediction of delamination initiation, since the transverse stresses predicted directly from the shell solution are of too low accuracy. This was recently done e.g. by Främby et al. [4] who complemented an XFEM shell formulation with a stress recovery approach – see e.g. [5] – performed over a patch of elements, thereby making the model fully adaptive. As for the alternative concept based on an isogeometric approach by Hosseini et al., there is a need to handle successive introduction of new discontinuities by means of knot-insertion in an automated fashion. A first step in this direction was taken by the authors in [6], outlining strategies for how to initiate and propagate delamination cracks using this framework. As a benefit over FE based C^0 continuous shells, the necessary improvements of the interlaminar stresses for isogeometric shells can be performed element-wise since in-plane stresses are smooth over element boundaries.

2 ISOGEOMETRIC CONTINUUM SHELL ELEMENT

The kinematic relations and the discretisation of the isogeometric continuum shell element are presented in detail in Hosseini et al. [1] and also summarised in Remmers and Fagerström [6]. Thereby, no details are given here. Instead, we give a summary of the most important features.

The continuum shell element under consideration is approximated purely with displacement degrees of freedom and has a finite thickness. Thus, it has a top and a bottom surface. The displacement approximation is constructed such that T-Splines are used for the in-plane shell approximation, which are then multiplied with a higher order B-spline approximation to construct the three-dimensional displacement approximation within the element. In this way, a B-spline volume patch is created by multiplying a bivariate and a univariate spline function. Because of the higher order continuity of the discretisation in thickness direction, the strain field varies at least linearly over the thickness, which is important to avoid thickness locking. Furthermore, the higher order continuity in-plane, as created by the T-Spline approximation, implies that stress gradients can be evaluated locally in an element with high accuracy. This possibility of evaluating stress gradients element-wise with high accuracy can be utilised when improving the prediction of through-thickness stress components which are generally predicted poorly in shell problems. And these stresses are needed to predict onset of delamination, thereby essential for an adaptive shell model.

2.1 Introducing weak and strong discontinuities in the displacement approximation

Spline functions, such as B-spline functions, are recursively defined entirely based on a so-called knot vector \mathcal{J} . As an example, a quadratic B-spline function with $\mathcal{J} = [0, 0, 0, 0.5, 1, 1, 1]$ is shown in Figure 1 (left). In fact, B-spline functions, as the ones used to construct the displacement field in the through-the-thickness direction for this shell element, are C^{p-k} continuous at a knot with multiplicity k [7]. This means that we are able to control the continuity of the basis functions at a knot by arbitrarily selecting its multiplicity. This property is useful in modelling traction-free cracks and adhesive interfaces (strong discontinuity) and layered structures with C^0 continuity between the layers (weak discontinuity) [11].

By initially adopting the through-thickness approximation for the shell as given by the knot vector $\mathcal{J} = [0, 0, 0, 0.5, 1, 1, 1]$, we obtain four basis functions through the thickness which are all C^1 continuous at the midsurface. We call this the lumped state. Now suppose that we want to have a composite shell consisting of two layers of equal thickness. The deformation of composite structures requires a unique displacement at the interfaces and different strain fields in the adjacent layers. In the example of Figure 1, this is simply achieved by having a displacement field which is C^0 continuous at the interface (the mid-surface in this case) and the knot vector $\mathcal{J} = [0, 0, 0, 0.5, 0.5, 1, 1, 1]$. Henceforth, we will denote this state of the element as the weakly discontinuous state. Subsequently, the complete separation of the layers is obtained if we insert the second knot as: $\mathcal{J} = [0, 0, 0, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 1, 1, 1]$, and this state of the element will be denoted as the discontinuous state. Figure 1 shows the corresponding basis functions through the knot insertion process.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of introducing a discontinuity in the thickness direction of a shell. Weak and strong discontinuities between the layers of a composite shell are created by knot-insertion.

3 IMPROVED PREDICTION OF THROUGH-THICKNESS STRESS COMPONENTS

Transverse out-of-plane stresses evaluated directly from the lumped shell element state are, as a consequence of the adopted simplified kinematics (as for any shell element), generally of poor quality. To still be able to obtain reliable predictions of these stresses as input to the update criterion, we adopt a strategy similar to Främby et al. [4] where improved values are recovered from the 3D momentum balance equations. Thus, we reconstruct the transverse stress variation through the thickness of the shell via thickness integration of these equations. For zero body forces under quasi-static conditions we can find the transverse stresses as:

$$\sigma_{13}^k = - \sum_{n=1}^k \int_{x_3^{n-1}}^{x_3^n} (\sigma_{11,1} + \sigma_{12,2}) dx_3 + C_1$$

$$\sigma_{23}^k = - \sum_{n=1}^k \int_{x_3^{n-1}}^{x_3^n} (\sigma_{21,1} + \sigma_{22,2}) dx_3 + C_2$$

$$\sigma_{33}^k = - \sum_{n=1}^k \int_{x_3^{n-1}}^{x_3^n} \int_{x_3^{n-1}}^{x_3^n} (\sigma_{11,11} + \sigma_{22,22} + 2\sigma_{12,12}) dx_3 dx_3 + C_3 x_3 + C_4$$

where $\sigma_{ij,k}$ denotes derivative of stress component σ_{ij} with respect to spatial coordinate x_k and where C_i are integration constants which can be used to adapt the reconstructed stresses to boundary conditions on the shell top and bottom surface.

Furthermore, since the integrations of the out-of-plane stress components involve the in-plane first and second derivatives of the in-plane stress components (indices 1 and 2), these need to be extracted from the solution. In traditional finite element analyses with shells, the in-plane stress components are predicted with good accuracy. However, the stress derivatives are not because of only C^0 in-plane continuity of the shape functions. Since the derivatives of these traditional shape functions are discontinuous across element edges, the resulting stresses are non-smooth also for elastic problems. The benefit from an IGA approach on the other hand is that stresses indeed are smooth when crossing element edges, and that, thereby, the derivatives of each component can be computed element wise with good accuracy.

With the current IGA approach, one way to calculate the stress gradients is to compute the third gradients of the displacement approximation, and then calculate the stress derivatives directly. However,

this requires a displacement approximation of at least order three, e.g. one degree higher than what is shown in Figure 1. As an alternative, one can make use of the stress smoothness and project in each element the stress variation in each plane of integration points on a second order Lagrangian basis (using conventional second order finite element shape functions). This projected stress field can then, for each layer of integration points, be used to evaluate first and second derivatives of each stress component in the element centre point at a given position through the thickness. As final step, we then integrate the stress derivatives to obtain the recovered stress profile. As a result, we obtain an accurate prediction of the through-the-thickness variation of the transverse stresses even when a lumped thickness discretisation is used, as shown in the numerical example.

4 NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

To demonstrate the potential of the proposed stress reconstruction, we consider a simply supported pressure loaded square plate with three plies $[0/90/0]$, as shown in Figure 2, for which an analytical solution has been derived by Pagano...

Figure 2: Schematic of the squared pressure loaded plate considered in the numerical example.

The properties in this particular example are taken from [8] in which a similar reconstruction is proposed and compared with the analytical solution. The properties are: $E_L = 25$ GPa, $E_T = E_{T'} = 1$ GPa, $G_{LT} = G_{LT'} = 0.2$ GPa, $G_{TT'} = 0.5$ GPa, $\nu_{LT} = \nu_{LT'} = \nu_{TT'} = 0.25$ where L refers to the fibre direction, T to the in-plane transverse direction and T' to the out-of-plane direction. Furthermore, the thickness of the plate is $h = 3$ mm and the side length is $a = b = 110$ mm and the pressure is applied as a sinusoidally varying pressure (as illustrated in the figure) with amplitude $p_0 = 1$ kPa.

The resulting prediction of the through-thickness variation of σ_{13} in a point ($x = 22.5$ mm, $y = 22.5$ mm) marked with a red dot in Figure 2, normalized with its maximum value in the centre of the plate, is shown as red dots in Figure 3 together with the analytical solution taken from [8] as a blue line. It is concluded that the through thickness variation is well predicted.

Figure 3: Through-the-thickness variation of σ_{13} at $x = 22.5$ mm, $y = 22.5$ mm for the plate problem considered in the numerical example. Red dots indicate the reconstructed stresses at the ply interfaces and the blue line indicates the analytical solution taken from [8].

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper we present an isogeometric continuum shell element in which the interpolation in thickness direction can be modified automatically in order to improve the accuracy of the element under high stress states and to model delamination growth. The use of isogeometric shape functions is essential here. It enables to introduce weak and strong discontinuities by knot insertion. Furthermore, the higher order continuity allows to reconstruct the rather poor stress representation of the through-thickness components. The numerical results show that the stress reconstruction yields accurate predictions of the out-of-plane shear stress in a pressure loaded composite plate. The application of the approach in large scale analyses however remains to be demonstrated.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Hosseini, J.J.C. Remmers, C.V. Verhoosel, and R. de Borst. Propagation of delamination in composite materials with isogeometric continuum shell elements. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 102(3-4):159–179, 2015.
- [2] J. Brouzoulis and M. Fagerström. An enriched shell element formulation for efficient modeling of multiple delamination propagation in laminates. *Composite Structures*, 126:196–206, 2015.
- [3] M. McElroy, Use of an enriched shell finite element to simulate delamination-migration in a composite laminate, *Composite Structures*, 167:88-95, 2017
- [4] J. Främby, M. Fagerström and J. Brouzoulis. Adaptive modelling of delamination initiation and propagation using an equivalent single-layer shell approach, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, DOI: 10.1002/nme.5536, 2017.
- [5] E. Carrera. A priori vs. a posteriori evaluation of transverse stresses in multilayered orthotropic plates. *Composite Structures*, 48(4):245-260, 2000.
- [6] J.J.C. Remmers and M. Fagerström, Strategies for modelling delamination growth using isogeometric continuum shell elements. In: *Proceedings of 17th European Conference on Composite Materials*, 2016.
- [7] L. Piegl and W. Tiller. *The NURBS Book*, Second Edition. Springer-Verlag, New York, 1997.
- [8] J.-E. Dufour, P. Antolin, G. Sangalli, F. Auricchio, A. Reali. A cost-effective isogeometric approach for composite plates based on a stress recovery procedure, arXiv:1704.06679v1 [cs.CE], 2017.